

Style for IRRN Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.
- Type all contributions double-spaced. ■

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Performance of a male-sterile IR36/KN361 population in Thailand

Somma Amonsilpa and Ben R. Jackson, Rice Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand

Interest in male sterility of rice as a means of enhancing the recombination of genes for important quantitative characters and evaluation of hybrid vigor for yield has recently increased. Singh and Ikehashi (*IRRN* 4[3]:3 1979) reported the induction of a genetic male-sterile recessive mutant from treatment of IR36 with ethyleneimine at IRRI. A few male-sterile plants that showed normal meiosis with complete restoration of fertility in the F₂ were identified. Outcrossing with the male-sterile plants was reported to vary from 15 to 34%. This is the first report of the performance of this male-sterile source outside IRRI.

One hundred-twenty-one plants from a bulk seed population of the cross male-sterile IR36/KN361 obtained from IRRI in April 1979 were transplanted in a screenhouse at the Bangkhen Rice Experiment Station in the 1979 dry season. The purpose was to assess their performance and to begin incorporation of the male-sterile character into adapted Thai varieties.

Details of male sterility in individual plants were not carefully recorded but the following observations may interest rice breeders.

- Eleven panicles representing different plants were bagged before flowering; 7 of them produced no seed and the other 4 gave less than 5% seed set.
- The seed set of all 121 plants was estimated visually and by counting all the seeds produced by each plant. The seeds were classified as:
 - Highly sterile (0–100 seeds/plant)
 - Moderately sterile (101–1,000 seeds/plant)
 - Normal fertile (1,000–3,000 seeds/plant)

The proportions found for each classification were:

- Highly sterile, 20 plants
- Moderately sterile, 69 plants
- Normal fertile, 32 plants

The easy recovery of highly sterile plants in a small population suggests that male sterility is a recessive character controlled by one or more genes. Many plants produced fewer than 10 seeds, which could have resulted from cross pollination. That suggests that rice breeders can incorporate male sterility into their own cultivars without undue difficulty. Through continuing studies we hope to obtain more precise data that will permit genetic analysis of male sterility under Thai conditions. ■

Sources of semidwarfism in locally developed varieties

T. R. Hargrove, editor, and V. L. Cabanilla, research assistant, Office of Information Services, International Rice Research Institute

A list of 370 improved rice varieties released in 36 countries in the post-IR8 era was compiled from records of the International Rice Genetic Survey (IRGS).

Seventy-four percent of the new varieties were semidwarfs. A third of the semidwarfs were IRRI lines or varieties released to farmers by national rice improvement programs; the other 183 cultivars were locally developed (LD) in national programs (see figure, A, B).

Using IRGS records we traced the ancestry of the 183 local semidwarfs, partly to determine the source of the dwarfing genes that gave them their short plant stature. IR8 (Peta/DGWG) was a parent of 40%; Taichung Native 1 (TN1) (DGWG/Tsai-yuan-chun), of 22%. The original semidwarfing gene source Dee-geo-woo-gen (DGWG) was a direct parent of only 2% (figure, C), although it appeared in the ancestry of almost all varieties. About 21% of the local